

Solution equilibria and synthetic studies of heterobinuclear complexes of DTPA with Cu^{II} and alkaline earth metal ions

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Abstract : The formation, stability and structures of heterobinuclear complexes of diethylenetriaminepentaacetic acid (DTPA) with Cu^{II}-alkaline earth metal ion systems have been studied in aqueous solution as well as in the solid state. All investigation have been done potentiometrically in the biologically relevant conditions and the stability constants have been evaluated using SCOGS computer program.

The stability sequence has been found as : CuLBe > CuLMg > CuLCa > CuLSr > CuLBe.

Keywords : DTPA, SCOGS, copper(II), binuclear complexes.

The study of interaction of EDTA type ligands with the metal ions cobalt and copper has elicited much interest since they promote the interaction of nucleic acids with amino acids in biological system leading to the formation of ternary complexes^{1,2}. Metal complexes of aminopolycarboxylate ligands have considerable biological relevance. Extensive and diversified application of polyaminocarboxylic acids have stimulated interest in the higher homologues such as diethylenetriaminepentaacetic acid (DTPA) or triethylenetriaminehexaacetic acid (TTHA) in order to develop ligands with an increase affinity and selectivity of metal detoxification³.

The formation, stability and thermodynamic studies of mixed metal complexes of biofunctional ligands have been reported to a lesser extent compared to mixed-ligand systems. Mutual influences between metal ions may be of antagonist or of synergistic nature⁴. The present paper is in continuation of our earlier work on mixed metal complex systems⁵. Some of the DTPA complexes have been utilized as contrast enhancing agents in biomedical magnetic resonance imaging (MRI)^{6,7}. This is the reason why the binary and ternary complexes with this ligand and its variously substituted derivatives have recently become the subject of extensive investigations in solution^{8,9} and in the solid state¹⁰⁻¹³. In this paper, by potentiometric titrations, we have determined the stability of the mixed-metal complexes of DTPA with Cu^{II}-alkaline earth metal and evaluated their solution behaviour. The hydrolysis of metal ion has been taken into account wherever it interfered with stability constant measurements. The heterobinuclear complexes of DTPA have been isolated

in solid state and studied by infra-red spectroscopy.

Experimental

All the reagents were of A.R. grade and their solutions were prepared in double-distilled CO₂-free water. Metal-nitrate solutions were standardised by complexometric EDTA titration¹⁴. 0.1 M solution of DTPA was prepared by weighing the requisite amount and dissolving it into two equivalents of alkali solution. Carbonate-free sodium hydroxide and sodium nitrate solutions were prepared in doubly distilled water and standardised as usual.

pH measurements were made with a century model CP 901-S pH-meter using a special glass electrode (accuracy ± 0.01 pH) at 35 ± 1 °C. The following sets of solutions were prepared and the initial volume in each case was made up to 50.0 ml with doubly distilled water.

Set I : 10.0 ml NaNO₃ (0.5 M) + 5.0 ml HNO₃ (0.02 M) + 35 ml H₂O.

Set II : 10.0 ml NaNO₃ (0.5 M) + 5.0 ml HNO₃ (0.02 M) + 10 ml DTPA (0.005 M) + 25.0 ml H₂O.

Set III : 10.0 ml NaNO₃ (0.5 M) + 5.0 ml HNO₃ (0.02 M) + 10.0 ml DTPA (0.005 M) + 10.0 ml Cu²⁺ (0.005 M) + 15.0 ml H₂O.

Set IV : 10.0 ml NaNO₃ (0.5 M) + 5.0 ml HNO₃ (0.02 M) + 10.0 ml DTPA (0.005 M) + 10.0 ml Cu²⁺ (0.005 M) + 10.0 ml M²⁺ (0.005 M) + 5.0 ml H₂O.

where M²⁺ stands for metal ion solutions of Be^{II}, Mg^{II}, Ca^{II} and Sr^{II}. All the solution mixtures were titrated individually against a carbonate free 0.1 M NaOH solution.

The other experimental details have been described elsewhere¹⁵. Proton-ligand and metal-ligand constants were calculated with the aid of SCOGS¹⁶ computer program, by VINTRON computer set. Preliminary estimates of binary and ternary constants obtained by Least square method¹⁷ were further refined by SCOGS. Ionic product of water (K_w) and activity coefficient of hydrogen ion under the experimental conditions were obtained from literature¹⁸.

The solid studies deals with the preparation and isolation of mixed-metal chelates of Cu^{II} -DTPA with Mg^{II} , Ca^{II} , Sr^{II} and Ba^{II} respectively. Their structural studies are conducted by elemental analysis, metal analysis, electrical conductance behaviour and infra-red spectra.

Preparation of complexes :

These ternary chelates were prepared by reacting the appropriate amount of ligand DTPA and the metal salts in requisite amount by keeping the molar ratio as 1 : 1 : 1. 0.01 moles of DTPA and 0.01 moles of cupric oxide were weighed and taken into a beaker 15–16 ml of distilled water was added into it. The solution was heated on a water bath with continuous stirring for one and a half hour at 50–90 °C. A clear blue solution was obtained. Then 0.01 moles of alkaline earth metal ions were weighed and added into this solution and again it was stirred for two hours at 50–90 °C. The pH of the solution was adjusted between 2 to 3. The metal complexes got separated and the precipitate was digested on the water bath, filtered over a buchner funnel, washed with ethanol and dried. The m.p., elemental analysis and conductivity measurements of these complexes were done (Table 1).

The infra-red absorption spectra of DTPA, the binary complex Cu^{II} -DTPA and the hetero-bimetallic chelates were recorded in the region 400–4000 cm^{-1} in Nujol

mulis region/KBr disc/ CsI/CHCl_3 with the help of Shimadzu spectrophotometer, model 820 IPC. The infra-red absorption frequencies of the heterobimetallic complexes are listed in Table 2.

Results and discussion

The ligand diethylenetriaminepentaacetic acid titrates as a pentaprotic acid (H_5L). Its $\text{p}K^{\text{H}}$ values 1.86, 2.79, 4.29, 8.02 and 10.49 correspond to successive deprotonation of the five-COOH groups. The distribution diagrams indicate that 1 : 1 : 1 mixed metal chelates are forming in all the cases. The stability constants of these complexes have been calculated according to eq. (1).

$$\beta_{\text{pqrst}} = \frac{[(\text{M}_1)_p (\text{M}_2)_q (\text{L})_r (\text{OH})_s]}{[\text{M}_1]^p [\text{M}_2]^q [\text{L}]^r [\text{OH}]^s} \quad (1)$$

β_{pqrst} is the overall stability constant of the complex and $\text{M}_1 = \text{Cu}^{\text{II}}$ while $\text{M}_2 =$ alkaline earth metal ions (i.e. Be, Mg, Ca, Sr and Ba). The term p, q, r are usually positive numbers or zero, s is a negative integer for a protonic species and a positive integer for a hydroxo species.

In the present study, following species have been detected from the computer analysis of the pH titration data; CuL , CuLBe , CuLMg , CuLCa , CuLSr , CuLBa in addition to the protonated ligand species. Table 3 represents the proton-ligand, metal-ligand binary and ternary constants ($\log \beta$) at 35 ± 1 °C in aqueous solution. The sequence found in the stability constants of Cu^{II} -DTPA-alkaline earth metal system is as follows :

$\text{CuLBe} > \text{CuLMg} > \text{CuLCa} > \text{CuLSr} > \text{CuLBa}$. Be^{2+} ion being the smallest in size has the highest value of stability constant in the ternary system.

The formation of binary and ternary complexes is

Table 1. Physical properties, analytical data and conductance behaviour of chelates

Formula	Colour	Decomposition temp. (°C)	Analysis (%) : Found (Calcd.)				
			C	H	N	Cu	M (2nd metal)
$\text{Mg}^{\text{II}}\text{-Cu}^{\text{II}}\text{-DTPA.4H}_2\text{O}$	Blue crystals	212	27.48 (26.12)	3.38 (2.91)	6.54 (6.57)	30.71 (30.12)	4.23 (4.10)
$\text{Ca}^{\text{II}}\text{-Cu}^{\text{II}}\text{-DTPA.4H}_2\text{O}$	Blue crystals	215	29.03 (25.26)	3.23 (2.92)	6.76 (6.30)	29.72 (30.81)	5.21 (7.69)
$\text{Sr}^{\text{II}}\text{-Cu}^{\text{II}}\text{-DTPA.4H}_2\text{O}$	Blue crystals	217	27.17 (24.33)	3.39 (2.26)	6.66 (5.57)	26.88 (27.07)	16.01 (17.29)
$\text{Ba}^{\text{II}}\text{-Cu}^{\text{II}}\text{-DTPA.4H}_2\text{O}$	Blue crystals	220	22.21 (22.04)	2.58 (2.38)	4.23 (5.46)	23.12 (22.22)	20.23 (21.24)

Table 2. Infra-red absorption table of DTPA and Cu^{II}-DTPA-alkaline earth metal complexes

Complexes	H ₂ O or ROH	-CH	-OH	-COOH	-COOM	-COOH
Ligand DTPA	3495.2	3024.0	2773.4	1732.0	-	1218.9
Cu ^{II} -DTPA	3406.1	2868.2	2736.2	1724.2	1606.6	1228.6
Mg ^{II} -Cu ^{II} -DTPA.4H ₂ O	3371.1	2962.5	2771.2	-	1600.8	1235.8
Ca ^{II} -Cu ^{II} -DTPA.4H ₂ O	3408.0	2954.7	2628.2	-	1595.0	1240.6
Sr ^{II} -Cu ^{II} -DTPA.4H ₂ O	3418.2	2976.0	2624.3	-	1604.7	1220.6
Ba ^{II} -Cu ^{II} -DTPA.4H ₂ O	3411.8	2995.2	2634.6	-	1587.3	1295.4

Table 3. Proton-ligand and metal-ligand binary and ternary constants (log β_{pqrst}) at 35 ± 1° in aqueous solution and I = 0.1 mol dm⁻³ NaNO₃

(a) Proton-ligand constants :

	p	q	r	s	t	log β _{oorot}
LH ₅	0	0	1	0	-5	27.45
LH ₄	0	0	1	0	-4	25.59
LH ₃	0	0	1	0	-3	22.80
LH ₂	0	0	1	0	-2	18.51
LH	0	0	1	0	-1	10.49

(b) Hydrolytic constants of Be^{II} aq. ion and metal-ligand binary constants :

Be(OH) ⁺	0	1	0	0	1	-5.77
Be(OH) ₂	0	1	0	0	2	-11.89
CuL	1	0	1	0	0	19.88
CuL(OH)	1	0	1	0	1	12.69

(c) Metal-ligand ternary constants :

CuLBe	1	1	1	0	0	24.16
CuLMg	1	1	1	0	0	23.92
CuLCa	1	1	1	0	0	23.58
CuLSr	1	1	1	0	0	23.12

governed according to the equilibria :

Formation of hydroxo species Be(OH)⁺, Be(OH)₂ have been taken into consideration as the buffer regions corresponding to metal-ligand complex formation equilibria are found to be overlapping with the hydrolytic equilibria of Be²⁺ (aq) ions

Moreover, formation of binary hydroxo species at higher pH may be explained by assuming the equilibrium :

The ligand DTPA has eight potential coordination sites. In binary complex, Cu^{II} blocks six coordination sites. In binary complex, Cu^{II} block six coordination sites, giving the distorted octahedral geometry due to Jahn-Teller effect, leaving two sites uncoordinated. The remaining coordination sites can be utilized to bind with alkaline earth metal ions to form mixed metal complex.

The main infra-red absorption peaks observed for ligand DTPA are at 3495.2, 3024.0, 2773.4, 1732.0 and 1218.9 cm⁻¹ representing H₂O or ROH vibration, -CH vibration, -OH vibration, -COOH vibration and -COOH vibration respectively. These infra-red peaks were supported by the observations of Morris and Busch¹⁹ the peaks observed for Cu^{II}-DTPA are at 3406.1, 2968.2, 2736.2, 1724.2, 1606.6 and 1228.6 cm⁻¹ representing H₂O or ROH, -CH, -OH, -C=O, -COOM and -C=O vibrations respectively. As compared to DTPA, the pres-

ence of -COOM vibration at 1606.6 cm^{-1} confirms the process of binary complexation. The peaks observed for ternary $\text{Cu}^{\text{II}}\text{-DTPA-}\text{M}^{\text{II}}$ complexes are given in the Table 2. It is evident that as compared to $\text{Cu}^{\text{II}}\text{-DTPA}$, there is no vibration corresponding to free carboxyl group at around $1700\text{-}1725.0\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in any of the synthesized heterobinuclear complexes.

The measured conductance of all these Cu-L-alkaline earth metal chelates are in the range of $141.68\text{-}145.25\ \Omega\text{ cm}^{-1}$.

On the basis of stability constant, the analytical data, electrical conductance and IR spectral data, the most probable structures of chelates have been proposed as described earlier. The probable structures of these mixed-metal complexes seem to be convincing, because stereochemistry of the compounds like $\text{Na}_2\text{Mg}^{\text{II}}\text{-EDTA}\cdot\text{xH}_2\text{O}$, $\text{Ba}^{\text{II}}\text{-Cu}^{\text{II}}\text{-EDTA}\cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\text{Na}_3\text{Ca}^{\text{II}}\text{-DTPA}\cdot\text{H}_2\text{O}$ have already been established and are reported in the literature¹⁹. Cu^{II} is six-coordinated giving octahedral geometry to the binary complex while Be^{II} is tetraordinated and the other alkaline earth metal ions are six-coordinated utilizing water molecules in the synthesized ternary complexes.

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